

CLASSIFICATION OF TODAY'S VARIETIES AND VARIETIES OF COLUMNAR APPLE ORCHARDS IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада Устунсимон олманинг келиб чиқиши, агротехник тадбирларни тўғри ўтказиш технологияси устунсимон олманинг дунёда энг кўп учрайдиган навлари ҳақидаги маълумотлар қайд этилган ҳамда устунсимон олманинг пайвандтаглари кенг ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Устунсимон олма, пайвандтаг, навлар, барг, дарахт, тадқиқотлар.

Abstract: In this article, information about the origin of the columnar apple, the technology of proper agrotechnical activities, the information about the most common varieties of the columnar apple in the world, and the grafts of the columnar apple are widely covered.

Key words: Columns, grafts, branches, leaves, trees, studies.

Аннотация: В данной статье широко освещены сведения о происхождении колонновидной яблони, технологии правильных агротехнических мероприятий, сведения о наиболее распространенных в мире сортах колонновидной яблони, прививках колонновидной яблони.

Ключевые слова: Яблоня колонновидная, прививка, сорта, лист, дерево, исследования.

Introduction

In the development of gardening on the basis of intensive technologies, it is important to choose varieties, develop suitable agrotechnical measures for them. In this regard, the work carried out in World gardening is admirable. In World horticulture, columnar apples (ruschada – kolonnovidnie yablони, in English – columnar apples) are considered as a separate species, manifested as "super-accelerated technology", that is, at the cost of not having the head (main) branches and branches of plants, only the fruit on the stem ends and yields. Thanks to this, it is possible to plant the garden "too dense" and get a very high yield per unit area of the surface [1-3]. But even abroad it is now distributed only on the land of the bud, on small farms. While the extremely dense location of fruit trees necessitates changing the agrotechnical activities that take place in one aspect, in the other aspect it is necessary to use a lot of manual force over a large area, which is unlikely to lead to an increase in the cost of the product.

Columnar apples are varieties of apples that have changed shape (Apple Sports). It was first identified by farmers in the United States in the 60s and 70s of the 20th century in the garden and bred by individual grafting in a nursery. On this basis, of the early varieties, Wijcik ("Vojak" variety) was created in Canada in 1964. Nowadays, columnar apples are grown in tomatoes in most horticultural developed countries [1-3].

Taking into account the soil and climatic conditions of our republic, in connection with the introduction of new technologies, varieties in horticulture, the implementation of scientific research work on the cultivation and preparation of seedlings of columnar apples in the conditions of the central region is an urgent issue. Taking into account the above, it is planned to carry out scientific research on the development of technology for bringing columnar apple varieties to our republic, connecting them to ferns, semi-Ferns, strong growing grafts.

In the study, the varieties of columnar apples Vasyugan, Medok, President, Jin, triumph, Ostankino, senator, currency and Moscow corals are studied by connecting to wild apple seed pods, semipakana MM106, pakana M9, as well as strong-growing vegetative proliferative grafts MM111.

A brief description of columnar apples. Descriptions are presented based on the characteristics presented in the regions where these varieties are created.

President. The semilow is a variety and is 2.5-2.8 m tall. Enters the early harvest, the fruits begin to ripen at a height of 30 cm from the ground. It gives a rich harvest every year, with an average yield of 8-10 kg/Bush. The fruits ripen in August, weigh 140-180 g, are oblong-round in shape, the color is green to yellow, and pink is sometimes distinguished from other varieties by its purple-red hue holi.

Jin. Low variety. The variety enters the crop in its second year, is considered resistant to adverse environmental conditions. The fruits are medium-sized 120-150 g, shiny-raspberry in color, the flesh is whitish, sour-sweet in taste, crunchy and strongly smelling. When the yield is taken in relation to one Bush, the average is 4-5 kg.

Triumph. A semi-detached Variety that ripens in the autumn months. Seedlings enter the crop from the second year after planting and bear fruit on average from 5-6 kg per 5-year-old period. The fruits of apples are on average 120-180 g, flat-spherical in shape, the peel is crispy, shiny, bright dark-red in color, the fruit flesh is sweet, when eaten, the taste of honey remains.

Ostankino. A semi-detached variety of early harvest, it does not exceed 2.5 m in height. The Variety has a high yield – 12-15 kg of fruits in 5-6 years. Pollinators need varieties, in which of course other columnar apples can be used as pollinators. Fruits ripen on average 100-140 g, in the second half of August. They are round, slightly flat in shape, the peel is rough, smooth,

the color of the coating is bright, red in color and there is a reddish-purple state. The flesh is whitish, succulent, sweet-sour in taste.

Senator. A medium-sized variety, it is considered a drought and heat resistant variety. The yield reaches up to 15-16 kg from one Bush. The average weight of its fruits is 130-180 g. the color of the coating is dark-red and is located in the form of margins. The fruit flesh is succulent, creamy-colored, gently smelling Apple. The preservation of fruits goes from December to January.

Currency. Quechpishar is a variety and is harvested and harvested in September. It is of particular importance for its resistance to Frost, diseases. Entering the crop for 2 years, 6-7 years bear fruit on average from 4-5 kg. The fruits are round-conical in shape, the peel is thin, the main one is yellow, and the covering hue is pink-red, occupying up to half of the fruit. The fruit flesh is succulent, whitish, strongly scented, slightly sweet in taste, but with a pronounced sourness.

In conclusion, the study of columnar apples, which is a novelty for Uzbek gardening, the issues of their introduction, the development of seedlings are an urgent issue and serve as an important factor in the development of the industry on the basis of intensive technologies.

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